

SUITABLE TECHNIQUES FOR THE LEARNING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Effective training methods are discussed in the article. Initially, it is noted that the "pomodoro" training method, which is one of the most effective, is divided into certain time intervals. In addition, it should be noted that one of the best qualities of Pomodoro technology is that it is very easy to use and does not require prior training. In addition, Feynman's approach is mentioned. In Feynman's method, the importance of explaining information in simple language is emphasized. The most effective strategies for increasing students' enthusiasm for learning are considered, as well as their advantages and ways of using them are mentioned in the article.

Keywords: methodology, method, training, training process, training.

Introduction

Lifelong learning is a term that includes general education, vocational training and education, formal and informal education to improve knowledge, skills and habits in personal, social and civic life.

Learning is generally a difficult process. That is to say, learning cannot be accomplished solely through reading books or articles about science. When we talk about lifelong learning, we mean that we have to keep up with all of life's events, read books, and occasionally even take trips to learn new things. Since fresh subjects and discoveries from everyday life are priceless. Thus, lifelong learning involves a variety of activities, such as watching educational films, conversing with knowledgeable and perceptive people, and occasionally just observing and analyzing. Additionally, using technological tools like computers, tablets, and phones, lifelong learning offers a learning process that is not limited by time or location.

It should go without saying that in order to improve the effectiveness and scope of our education, we must investigate, apply, and select the most appropriate options. Let's investigate some learning strategies.

Main part

The Pomodoro technique is a time management strategy that divides a 25-minute period of concentrated work into five-minute segments. The Italian word for tomato, "Pomodoro", refers to each work variety.

Francesco Cirillo, the man who invented the Pomodoro technique, used a tomato-shaped kitchen timer to set up work intervals while he was a college student in the late 1980s.

Cirillo experimented with varying work intervals, ranging from two minutes to an hour. It didn't take him long to realize that an hour was too long to concentrate on one thing. Cirillo concluded that twenty-five minutes would be the best for his purposes.

Through the use of restorative breaks and limiting the amount of time spent attempting to maintain focus, the Pomodoro Technique essentially helped people focus better on tasks.

Application of the Pomodoro technique has been summerised below. The Pomodoro technique's ease of use and lack of training requirements are among its best features.

Cirillo primarily uses the Pomodoro technique in five areas:

- a) Make your to-do list, first.
- b) Schedule twenty-five minutes, and don't stop working on your task until that time has passed.
- c) Noting that you've finished one session when the allotted time runs out
- d) Take a five-minute break.
- e) Take a long 15–30 minute break after completing four more pomodoro sessions in this manner.

However, how should these materials be used?

A list of everything you need is listed to accomplish each day to ensure you get the most out of your Pomodoro sessions. If you have a long list, don't freak out. You will split up the work you have throughout the day to make it easier to manage. All you have to do is write down what you need to get done today.

To fully experience the Pomodoro technique, use a real timer instead of copying the Cirillo technique and using a tomato-shaped kitchen timer. For this, you can use a real or virtual timer.

You should be able to work uninterruptedly on the task or tasks of your choice for 25 minutes after you set the timer. Handling distractions is a difficult task that may require some time to finish. If you are utilizing the Pomodoro technique, try to alert people nearby. By doing this, disruptions and outside distractions may be lessened. During Pomodoro, if you have free time and are unsure of what to work on, use it to organize and enhance your work. Before the timer goes off, consider the tasks you've completed or write down the lessons you've learned.

After you've used up all of the allotted time during a study session, you can take a five-minute break. Think about filling your water bottle or grabbing a snack during this time. Rest your eyes, and if you can, try to spend less time in front of the screen. Get up and move your body, extending your legs. Maintaining your health will enable you to maintain your motivation for the remainder of the day.

You should perform the initial four actions four times. Proceed directly to step six after completing all four Pomodoros, omitting step four.

After finishing four steps in application of Pomodoros, take a longer break. Aim for fifteen to twenty minutes. During this break, you can eat or take a brief stroll outside. Use the break wisely, whatever it may be.

In order to improve productivity, the Pomodoro technique also assists you in developing disciplined

habits. Short breaks, however, have also been shown to aid in user focus. Of course, it can be challenging to develop effective time management and productivity strategies for each individual. Nonetheless, experimenting with different approaches and personalizing the task can prove to be effective time management strategies.

The significance of providing information in an understandable manner is emphasized by the Feynman method. Richard Phillips Feynman, a theoretical physicist, is responsible for the technique's name. He was awarded the Physics Nobel Prize. One method for making complex information understandable is the Feynman technique. The four sections of the method are described in the section on training and research below.

- Performs term processing;
- Defines and contextualizes the research object;
- Reviews and analyzes the data;
- Rewords the text in your own words.

To define and contextualize the research object you should take out a pen and paper to begin the practice. Jot down the idea that you want to expand on. Put the term at the folio's top.

Continuing from the last stage, you now have to define the concept. Assume you wish to explain to someone who is unfamiliar with the topic the salient points of that knowledge. What information would you like to give him so that he is aware of the main points of the situation?

You can pretend to introduce the subject aloud to a listener after finishing the writing exercise. In this manner, you can determine whether you are having trouble conveying the information or whether you have what you need to make your point.

You are encouraged to review the earlier sections by using the Feynman method. Read the text you prepared with the concept's exposition and description very carefully for this topic. Which details, in your opinion, are not sufficiently clear? What adjustments would you like to see made to the text to make it more readable? And what other details would you like to include? Examine your writing carefully. and went over the content multiple times.

You can learn more about a subject than you might have known previously by using developmental reading. In other words, you are able to weigh the knowledge you currently possess against the knowledge you still lack. Reviewing the exercise is crucial in order to pinpoint its advantages and disadvantages. There should be content expansion in addition to exercise. As a result, consult data sources when reviewing and evaluating content.

Recall that it's critical to be able to explain information to a person who doesn't know it already. It is therefore best to avoid using language that is too technical or detailed. Stated differently, it facilitates the exhibition's processing even more. Write creative, succinct, and clear text. The main points of the problem should be covered in the text.

A general theme of four steps is suggested by the Feynman method. Students are encouraged to participate actively in this process. Because all four sections are seamlessly connected, they provide a clear outline

for how to present the material in an easy-to-understand manner. This is an approach that can be used even when studying subjects with extremely complex material.

Internal factors influence motivation. No one can be forced to adopt it from the outside. Attempting to impart their own motivations to their offspring is one of the most common mistakes parents make. Nonetheless, it's essential to establish a setting that encourages their intrinsic motivation.

It's easy to understand the motivation formula: activity + satisfaction = motivation. A person will always make an effort to avoid situations that are stressful or demanding. A person can be inspired to participate in any activity if you provide the conditions necessary for him to succeed and feel good about himself. This will serve as the motivational engine within. Recall the moments when you were highly motivated. This, of course, occurred while you were engaged in an enjoyable activity. The way children learn is governed by the same principle. The use of directive and cautionary phrases like "study your lessons", "work hard", "be responsible", and "get high grades" when discussing education and school associates learning with unpleasant feelings like tension and anxiety. Conversely, encouraging statements like "I'm glad to see you studying", "I'm glad you don't give up in the face of challenges", "you have intriguing ideas", and "you express yourself very well" motivate kids to learn.

However, don't confine your child's education to the classroom if you want him to become a happy adult and a successful student. While academic knowledge and skills play a significant role in fostering children's intellectual and social growth, the family is primarily responsible for shaping their behavioral, emotional, and thought patterns. For your child to succeed in the world of ideas and knowledge, you must provide support. Higher academic outcomes will result from his education reflecting the family's passion for learning and exploration.

Youngsters who enjoy reading are also eager to learn. Individuals who struggle with reading also struggle with learning. Children who read regularly improve their vocabulary, grasp of ideas, and communication skills. Youngsters who read fluently acquire strong learning skills in all subject areas, including science and math.

Make reading a regular part of your children's lives. Tell children stories and fairy tales on a regular basis. Provide a good example for them by reading books and other materials yourself. You can also schedule regular reading sessions at home where family members read books together. Bring new books and other printed materials home every time. Talk about and share thought-provoking articles you occasionally come across with them. Prove that reading is an engaging and enjoyable pastime. Children lose interest in and motivation for reading when they believe it to be uninteresting. Allow them to select books on their own, provide reading assistance, and engage in enjoyable activities.

Children who are either overly or not at all supervised are among the reasons they drop out of school. It is appropriate to assist kids in their educational journey.

However, they must oversee this procedure on their own. Give kids the freedom to make choices and let them actively participate in the learning process both at home and at school. For instance, the child's decision about the subject of the writing assignment and their selection of extracurricular activities may be to blame. Children will be more interested and motivated in this process if they are given more chances to make choices and participate in the creation of the learning environment, activities, and techniques.

Encourage your student or child to talk about their experiences in school as well as some family issues. Establish an environment of open communication so that he can share his preferences. Whether you agree with them or not, express your respect for their viewpoints by offering your full support. When they believe that their opinions are unimportant or ignored, children stop participating in the educational process. When kids and teenagers understand that their opinions count and can be freely expressed without worrying about being disregarded, mocked, or judged, their learning abilities grow.

The learning process will be more enjoyable for the child the more areas and topics that pique his interest are included. Encourage your child to participate in subjects that pique his interest more if you truly want him to be an excellent student. If he has a fascination with dinosaurs, for instance, give him toys, books, stories, movies, and other materials on the subject. Next, ask him to list his top five dinosaurs and provide an explanation for his selections. A child typically investigates subjects that he finds engaging and enjoyable, which helps him become a better researcher and learner and subsequently improves his learning in other areas.

Determining a child's perception type is crucial to helping him learn more effectively. While some kids use one dominant form of perception while learning, others use multiple types. Utilizing the appropriate techniques can improve a child's learning quality and comprehension rate by determining the learning styles that suit him best. There are various forms of learning, including visual (vision), auditory, kinesthetic (experiential), literacy, logical, social (group), individual, etc. For instance, it is more appropriate to explain concepts to children of the auditory type verbally or by listening, as children of the visual type learn best when they see processes with their eyes. Children often use a variety of types, depending on the subject matter. Differentiating and implementing learning styles is more appropriate, particularly for young children.

It's easy to spread enthusiasm. The adage that children emulate their parents is not meaningless. Making good changes in yourself is the best way to have a positive influence on kids. Your child will undoubtedly be eager to learn if you are constantly eager to grow and learn. Do new research, read books, conduct experiments, and demonstrate to your child that learning is an exciting journey in any subject that interests you, whether it be science, literature, history, mathematics, or another area. Don't let the opportunity to work on a project or learn something together pass you by without exerting pressure or squeezing the child. Your child will be more interested in learning new things when

they witness the joy and excitement that education brings into your life.

The use of game-based learning has been around for a while, particularly in western nations. This approach raises children's motivation to learn while also enabling them to acquire deeper learning and non-knowledge abilities. The brain enjoys learning a new system while playing games, whether they are "serious" (like a war game) or lighthearted (like video games). The body's dopaminergic pleasure transmitters are triggered during this process. Playing enjoyable games makes kids more eager to engage in the educational process.

In addition to boosting group learning enthusiasm, game-based learning has a positive impact on the classroom learning process. Play is when kids really use their potential, not in the classroom. For them, games are more appealing. The games include a competitive aspect as well. Children compete in this period to battle, score points, and win for themselves, the team, or the opportunity to be re-inducted into the group.

Parents and educators have a fantastic opportunity to apply new ideas, grammar concepts, or knowledge in a way that promotes learning through play-based learning

Ask the child what he learned today and even ask him to teach you what he learned, rather than asking him about his grades when he gets home from school. Pay more attention to the child's learning than to their performance. Although outcomes are crucial, you can help him feel that genuine learning is more significant than grades and that you are more concerned about him by putting more emphasis on his learning process. Consolidating knowledge and allowing the child to express what he has learned in his own words are two benefits of attending to his learning process.

For your child to be motivated to learn, it is crucial that you assist them in organizing their supplies, notebooks, and homework. Even though disorganization is a trait of young schoolchildren, it can occasionally cause a sense of overload in the minds of those youngsters. Kids who are overloaded with information tend to feel more frustrated and anxious, which makes them less likely to study. Assist your child with homework and school supplies on a regular and gentle basis. In this scenario, his motivation to learn will rise and he will feel less worn out.

Whatever the scope, it's critical to acknowledge and applaud a child's accomplishments. Students in elementary school, in particular, require this kind of continuous support to maintain a high level of motivation and progress in their learning. This entails acknowledging and applauding accomplishment rather than rewarding passable performance. When a student completes challenging homework, a parent should write them a note. (Warning!!! Rewarding kids for their learning outcomes requires caution. When rewards are abused, kids may come to believe that learning is pointless in and of itself and that obtaining rewards is the primary objective. We'll soon publish a different piece on the subject of rewards in education.)

When a child is very weak and struggles in many areas, it can be challenging to identify and focus on

their strengths. For a child's emotional and intellectual development to be in a healthy state, it is crucial to emphasize their strengths. This is yet another example of the kind of encouragement that keeps kids motivated to learn. Conversely, drawing attention to a child's shortcomings can make him feel hopeless, depressed, and less motivated to learn. For instance, it goes without saying that a child should get more help in math if he scored poorly on the test. But don't forget to congratulate him on a well-deserved grade in a different subject.

Conclusion

Although the phrase "learning every day" may seem odd, when used properly, it can be very beneficial. We should encourage the child to ask questions, investigate his surroundings, and draw logical conclusions whenever possible. We should assist him in organizing, classifying, and critically thinking about the things he observes and encounters. The child's intrinsic motivation to learn in the classroom, at home, and elsewhere will rise as a result of this strategy.

In my opinion, employing these strategies and tactics will help you streamline your learning process and make it easier, more productive, and memorable all at once.

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